

Studies in the Formation and Properties of Carbon-sulphur Surface Complexes. Part I. Formation on Treatment of Charcoal with Carbon Disulphide and Hydrogen Sulphide

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Treatment of sugar and coconut charcoals, containing different amounts of combined oxygen and hydrogen, with carbon disulphide or hydrogen sulphide results in appreciable fixation of sulphur, the effect being maximum at 600°. The amount of sulphur fixed decreases with decrease in the hydrogen and oxygen contents of the charcoal. The results indicate that the fixation of sulphur involves addition at the unsaturated sites and substitution of hydrogen or oxyhydrogen groups present on the charcoal surface.

In comparison to a considerable amount of work that has been reported in recent years on the formation and properties of carbon-oxygen solid complexes, as has been summed up in some excellent reviews covering over 500 references¹⁻³, it appears that very little work has been done on carbon-sulphur solid complexes. Fixation of certain amounts of sulphur on treatment of charcoal or carbon black with sulphur, carbon disulphide, or hydrogen sulphide, giving rise to carbon-sulphur solid complexes, has, however, been reported⁴⁻⁷. It was thought of interest to study the optimum conditions for the formation of such complexes on treating charcoal, before as well as after outgassing at different temperatures, with carbon disulphide and hydrogen sulphide and to gain some insight, if possible, into the mechanism of fixation of sulphur in this manner.

EXPERIMENTAL

Charcoals.—Sugar and coconut charcoals were prepared by carbonisation of recrystallised cane sugar and coconut shells⁸ and were used as such (when these are referred to as 'original' charcoals in the text) as well as after outgassing⁹ at 300°, 500°, 700°, 1000°, and 1200° so as to get materials of varying oxygen and hydrogen contents. Sugar charcoal was essentially free of ash, but coconut charcoal was 'deashed' on treatment with hydrofluoric acid to lower its ash content to < 0.2%.

Treatments.—Charcoal (10. g., oven-dried at 120°) was taken in a rotating (30-35 rotations/min.) silica tube (18" × 3/4") which could be heated in a tube furnace (15" × 1")

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electrically to any desired temperature up to 800° . Hydrogen sulphide (prepared in a Kipp apparatus using c.p. reagents, washed with potassium hydrogen sulphide and dried over calcium chloride columns) or carbon disulphide vapour (obtained on heating the liquid, c.p. Merck variety, in a water bath) was led over @1.5 litre/hr. The rotation of the tube kept the charcoal in constant tumbling motion. In each case the air in the tube was first displaced by flushing in hydrogen sulphide gas or carbon disulphide vapour, as the case might be, before raising the temperature. The treatment was carried out at first for 8 hr. at different temperatures and then at the optimum temperature for different intervals of time. At the end of the process, the supply of the gas was cut off, the product was allowed to cool, and then withdrawn and extracted with carbon disulphide in a Soxhlet extractor for a week (10 hr. a day) to remove any adhering or physically adsorbed sulphur. The final product was dried in an air oven (120°) and then stored in well-stoppered bottles flushed with nitrogen. The combined sulphur was estimated by Eschka's method¹⁰. The results were compared in a few cases with those obtained by microanalysis technique, carried out by Weiler and Strauss, Oxford, England, on request.

Adsorption of Bromine.—The fixation of bromine by charcoal, before as well as after treatment with carbon disulphide or hydrogen sulphide, was determined by the method described earlier⁸.

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows that the amount of sulphur fixed by charcoal increases with rise in the temperature of the treatment up to 600° and decreases thereafter, probably due to instability of the complex. The treatment for 6 hr. at this optimum temperature was found to be sufficient to obtain the maximum fixation of sulphur.

FIG. 1.

10. Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", D. Van Nostrand Co., Inc., N. Y., 1938, p. 906.

The amounts of sulphur fixed by sugar and coconut charcoals, on treatment with carbon disulphide or hydrogen sulphide under these optimum conditions, are plotted in Fig. 2 and 3 against the temperatures at which the charcoals have been outgassed prior to the treatments. The oxygen and hydrogen contents of the charcoals before the treatments are also plotted in the same figures. The fixation of sulphur in the case of sugar as well as coconut charcoal, more particularly on treatment with carbon disulphide, appears to fall more with decrease in hydrogen than in oxygen content. The presence of hydrogen in the charcoal probably facilitates decomposition of carbon disulphide to hydrogen sulphide, sulphur, and carbon

in addition to thermal decomposition. The amount of sulphur fixed on treatment with carbon disulphide is seen to be more than that fixed on treatment with hydrogen sulphide in the case of the original as well as the 300°- and 500°-outgassed sugar charcoals which contain appreciably large amounts of hydrogen (cf. curve II, Fig. 2). The values obtained with both the treatments are, however, fairly close to one another in the 700°, 1000°- and 1200°-outgassed charcoals containing much smaller amounts of hydrogen.

FIG. 2. Sulphur fixed in relation to oxygen and hydrogen contents of sugar charcoal outgassed at different temperatures.

FIG. 3. Sulphur fixed in relation to oxygen and hydrogen contents of coconut charcoal outgassed at different temperatures.

As the amount of sulphur fixed decreases appreciably with decrease in the hydrogen and oxygen contents of the charcoal, even on treatment with hydrogen sulphide, it appears probable that the fixation of sulphur is, in part at least, due to interaction with hydrogen or oxyhydrogen functional groups on the charcoal surface¹¹.

It may be noted that the maximum amounts of sulphur fixed by the original sugar and coconut charcoals (which contain maximum amounts of oxygen and hydrogen) are as high as 12 and 14 m.e./g. which correspond to 19.2 and 22.4 g./100 g. respectively.

The decomposition of such a stable gas as hydrogen sulphide in presence of charcoal at such a low temperature as 100° (Fig. 1), resulting in the fixation of sulphur, indicates strong valency forces operating along the carbon surface.

The treatments with carbon disulphide and hydrogen sulphide were found to cause elimination of appreciable amounts of hydrogen from the charcoal, as shown in Table I. There seems to be no relationship, however, between the amount of sulphur fixed and that of hydrogen eliminated. In the case of the samples rich in hydrogen, a good deal of hydrogen appears to escape as such on account of sweeping action of gaseous carbon disulphide or hydrogen sulphide, as the case may be.

TABLE I

Samples.	Temp. of treatment.	*H ₂ content.		*H ₂ eliminated.	*H ₂ S formed.	*Sulphur fixed.
		Initial.	Final.			
A. Treatment with carbon disulphide.						
Original	600°	33.9	9.7	24.2		12.2
Outgassed at 500°	500°	33.3	21.7	11.6		7.7
Do	600°	33.3	10.3	23.0	4.8	12.7
Do	700°	33.3	6.4	26.9		10.5
Outgassed at 700°	500°	22.0	13.9	8.1		7.6
Do	600°	22.0	10.0	12.0	2.1	9.1
Outgassed at 1000°	600°	11.4	6.7	4.7	2.0	5.0
Outgassed at 1200°	600°	10.2	2.3	7.9		3.1
B. Treatment with hydrogen sulphide.						
Original	600°	33.9	17.9	16.0		7.6
Outgassed at 1000°	600°	11.4	11.1	0.3		5.5
Outgassed at 1200°	600°	10.2	8.0	2.2		4.0

* Expressed in m.e./g.

As shown earlier⁸, a definite amount of surface unsaturation results in charcoals on the elimination of carbon dioxide complex on heating in 600-700° temperature range and it can be measured by the amount of bromine fixed by the charcoals on treatment with aqueous bromine. Since the charcoals in the present investigations had been heated at

600° in a current of hydrogen sulphide or carbon disulphide, most of the carbon dioxide complex had been eliminated. In order to find out how far the fixation of sulphur took place at the unsaturated sites created thereby, some of the samples after fixation of sulphur on treatment with carbon disulphide or hydrogen sulphide were treated with aqueous bromine in the usual way⁸. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Samples.	Sulphur fixed (m.e./g.).	Bromine fixed (m.e./g.).
A. Sugar charcoal.		
700°-outgassed charcoal:		
Before treatment	Nil	3.85
After treatment with CS ₂ at 200°	1.51	3.42
400°	3.18	2.48
500°	7.55	Traces
600°	8.10	Nil
700°	7.48	Nil
After treatment with H ₂ S at 600°	6.47	Nil
1000°-outgassed charcoal:		
Before treatment	Nil	3.76
After treatment with CS ₂ at 600°	4.99	Nil
After treatment with H ₂ S at 600°	5.50	Nil
1200° -outgassed charcoal:		
Before treatment	Nil	3.72
After treatment with CS ₂ at 600°	3.13	0.20
After treatment with H ₂ S at 600°	3.95	Nil
B. Coconut charcoal.		
1000°-outgassed charcoal:		
Before treatment	Nil	3.68
After treatment with CS ₂ at 600°	5.50	Nil
1200° -outgassed charcoal:		
Before treatment	Nil	3.76
After treatment with CS ₂ at 600°	3.60	Nil

It is seen that the amount of bromine fixed decreases after fixation of sulphur in every case and that when the amount of sulphur fixed is nearly equal to or in excess of that of bromine fixed by the same charcoal before the treatment with carbon disulphide or hydrogen sulphide, there is little or no further fixation of bromine. This shows that sulphur enters the charcoal at the same unsaturated sites where bromine can add itself. Further, since 1200° -outgassed charcoals (sugar as well as coconut shell), which contain very little of oxygen or hydrogen, can fix nearly the same amounts of sulphur as of bromine, it is evident that in such cases the mechanism of fixation of sulphur is exactly the same as that of fixation of bromine, i.e. addition at the unsaturated sites created by elimination of the CO₂-complex. But since the charcoals outgassed at lower temperatures, which contain appreciable amounts of hydrogen

and oxygen, can fix more of sulphur than of bromine (cf. 700°-outgassed charcoal in Table II), in such cases a part of the sulphur appears to be fixed also in replacement of hydrogen or oxyhydrogen groups present on the charcoal surface.

These observations indicate therefore that the fixation of sulphur by charcoal, leading to the formation of carbon-sulphur solid complex, involves two different reactions: addition at the unsaturated sites and substitution of hydrogen or oxyhydrogen groups present on the charcoal surface.

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